

**Depiction of Male Characters in
The Better Man by Anita Nair**

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Introduction :

Anita Nair is an Indian novelist who made her mark by not conforming to the prevalent trends in Indian English Literature. She has chosen her own way of writing and thus, also became the best seller and not only in the terms of the number of books sold (that we all know can be done by hiring one of the best book marketing companies in India) but also in garnering the opinions and critically valued appreciation from the book and literature critics in India. She has tried hard to become (but does not acknowledge) the voice of true feminism in the contemporary Indian English literature, not like Shoba De and others who have rather turned feminism into a show where you get to see unnecessary demands of headless equality with men rather than essential necessities that can change the actual situations on the ground for women. We will look into the male characters of Anita Nair in this article.

The Better Man is about the hero Mukundan and men characters related with him. The novel is set in a little town of Kaikkurussi in Northern Kerala. In the beginning of the novel, the painter Bhasi presents himself in the accompanying words: "Perhaps you have seen me. Perhaps you have not. On most days you can

find me glued to the side of some sun- speckled, age spotted wall. A human lizard with brushes for claws and can for a tail” (*TBM* 3). Bhasi considers himself as an ordinary man with no outstanding virtues.

Nevertheless, in reading the faces of the needy, he tries to extend his help to Mukundan. In the case of Mukundan, Bhasi says: “In you I saw a friend and a customer. Someone whose feeling have to be aided. You needed me” (*TBM*11). Bhasi decides to help Mukundan and insists that Mukundan should disclose the factors that disturb him. Bhasi says:

“Tell me, Mukundan. Tell me what it is that haunts you so. Tell me of the darkness that clouds your life. Tell me why you fold your handkerchief in eight precise squares... Tell me what makes perfection so important to you. Tell me why you have about you the smell of a haunted animal” (*TBM*11).

This is one of the illustrations of human behaviouristic pattern presented in the novel. By disposition, Bhasi varies generally from Vishnu, town cleric and Power House Ramakrishnan who appreciates an edge over others subsequent to winning a lottery. Bhasi does not have a place with the group of Shankar, tea club proprietor or Post Man Unni or Barber Nanu or the town proclaimer, Pavitran. He is not care for flavor shop proprietor CheKutty. These are a portion of the social totems that are promptly accessible in the novel.

Consequently to avoid this horrid state of affairs and to overcome his isolation, he takes alcohol but the drink lost its ability to suppress his fears. Unable to bear his destiny, he feels, “long, silent days as he plotted and planned his escape from the confines of its walls and the tyranny of his father Now this was his home, though he knew deep in his heart that it would never ever feel like home.”(*TBM*20)

Mukundan is inactive as there is no place to visit or one person to meet to entertain a cordial relationship. He feels very lonely as he is not able to associate with the locals inhabitants of the village: “He had made absolutely no effort to create a new life for himself.” (*TBM* 100) Even Achuthan Nair keeps update about the gossips of the village through barber Nanu. But Mukundan was idle and lonely. As a result, Mukundan decides to make his presence recognized in the village.

Shankar's Tea Club is the heart of the village. If Mukundan needs to continue his life in the village, he has to make friends here. He wears mundu and feels very happy about the renovation happened in him. He comes to know about Power House Ramakrishnan. All the regular visitors of the shop praise him for his munificence and his quality of forging friendship with all the VIPs around the area. Mukundan dreams of occupying his father's position in the village but one gives a damn care about him. While Mukundan is trying hard to reach the position of his father, villagers are naturally attracted towards Power House Ramakrishnan.

Bhasi fears the separation after Mukundan: "Rejection will drain my power to heal. And I fear that I shall be reduced to who I was when we first met: Painter Bhasi. One screw-loose Bhasi." (TBM 187). Bhasi is a perfect example of the above description of the male as sorted by Robert Stoller. The general population of that town calls him 'One-Screw-Loose Bhasi'. Bhasi reveals himself on the planet he has made like his dominance over the crossbreed framework, which is advanced out of the blend of a few solutions. His name is Bhaskaran Chandran. He has an advanced education in Botany and a Post-graduate Degree in English Language and Literature.

In his words: "The human body has a natural inbuilt capacity to heal itself to safeguard against trauma and disease. All I do is reinforce that natural vitality. I do not work miracles. I do not wave a wand to kill diseases. I simply find a remedy for the body to fight that disease" (TBM 9).

Mukundan is an elderly bachelor and a retired government employee who shares his life with other bachelors. As Indira Nityanandam comments: *The Better Man* by Anita Nair is the story of Mukundan who returns after retirement as a Government servant to his native village Kaikurussi. Set in idyllic surroundings, the novel explores the loneliness of many individuals of the village. Loneliness is the leit-motif of this novel and the novelist is able to create the *karuna rasa* by her depiction of these characters.

Mukundan is working as the librarian in the club library: "To Mukundan the library took the place of a family and allowed him to don the role of head of a household. He cares for it and provided for it and unlike human beings it demanded little from him and claim no rights" (TBM 14). When he is a kid he has the propensity for replicating down long sections from writers like Brontes, Dickens, Goldsmith and Chesterton. His father throws away all his writings when he has found his compositions. He announces: "No son of mine is going to waste his life trying to be a

writer”. He always tries to control the life of his son. Again, this is one cultural backdrop in which one witnesses a father as swaying between colonialism and the native culture. To quote Denise Riley: Any attention to the life of a woman, if traced out carefully, must admit the degree to which the effects of lived gender are at least sometimes unpredictable, and fleeting.

The landing of the old supervisor, Krishnan Nair is of great help to Mukundan. His choice to continue his old part gives Mukundan amazement. At the point when Mukundan is solicited to take up part from a commanding male for the sake of marriage, Mukundan debilitates Krishnan Nair.

He says: “It is much too late to talk of all that now. Who will give his daughter to a fifty-two-year-old man? And, if the purpose of the marriage is progeny, then she will have to be young and of child bearing age. Let’s not talk about pointless things” (*TBM* 39).

Krishnan Nair plays the part of a female victim position. He tries to please Mukundan with his cooking. Mukundan awakens from lay down with frightful dreams. Krishnan Nair lets him know: “Your mother could have prevented what was happening to her. The heartbreak. The humiliation. However, she chose to remain a victim. So don’t go about feeling guilty for what happened to her” (*TBM* 44).

Thus the depiction of male characters in the novel *The Better Man* is absolutely beautiful and the readers can certainly connect themselves with the characters portrayed in this novel. The artistic elements found in these novel forces every critic to say positive things urges everyone to read. Not only female victims but also male victims can be seen in this society must have been the thought process of the novelist.

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